

Text Classification on General Expense Dataset using Machine Learning in Business Operations

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Abstract: Many organizations are using Microsoft excel files to record and store enterprise data. Excel is a powerful tool to perform powerful computations on numerical data, but it has limitations in analysing non-numerical text data. Data mining tools underpinned by machine learning algorithms provide the platform to perform text analytics on documents and datasets containing textual data. Development of text analytical models is providing solutions to simple text classification problems inherent in raw enterprise datasets for the organizations. Ability to classify and label texts into appropriate categories is useful to generate aggregate reporting from detail transactional data, such as purchasing expenditure. Machine learning provides a unique opportunity to classify General Expense (GE) streams into appropriate categories for reporting and evaluations of expenditure items. This case study, project GEML, analyses and implements two popular machine learning models, SVM and Naïve Bayes, on a sample dataset to solve a text classification problem. The implementation process is executed through a CRISP-DM cycle, and the result confirms SVM as the optimum text classifier model.

Keywords: SVM Text Classifier, Naïve Bayes Classifier, Expenditure Item Categorisation, Text Classification, Machine Learning

1. Introduction

Project GEML is an acronym coined using key words from the topic of this paper on text classification modelling on GE dataset using Machine Learning. Departments at PNGUoT predominantly use excel files to record details of the disbursements of their annual operational expenditure. The purchasing transactions are sourced from the GE (General Expense) forms and manually entered into excel table files. A GE form is a manual requisition order form that gets completed by end-user departments to initiate a procurement process. The attribute of interest is particulars, which is a free text field found on a GE form. It captures the details of expenditure line items to procure.

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Project GEML examines a GE dataset from the Mathematics and Computer Science (MCS) department, and presents a text classifier model to reliably label the expenditure items according to the two given expenditure classes. The model outputs the original dataset with an extra column inserted and appropriately labelled to indicate whether the expenditure item is associated with a Goods or Services type of expenditure. Classification is also known as categorization or labelling of text, from a given set of text or document (Iguar and Segui, 2017).

GE process is a manual procurement process that facilitates requisitions and payments of goods & services (G&S) expended by respective departments of PNGUoT. The key stakeholders being the End-users or Originators (Finance/Admin officers at respective departments), the Approvers (Head of respective Departments) and the Accounts/Bursary team who are also the custodians of the GE process. Purchase requisitions are initiated by the end-user departments, which are then routed through the approval routes, approved and converted into official purchase orders. The vendor supplies the requested G&S with the invoice, and the Accounts team matches and settles the invoice to complete a GE process cycle. Other cash payments also require GE documentations for accounting and auditing purposes.

AGE paper form is a pre-printed document for the end-users to fill-out basic procurement information such as vendor name, date, department name, line particulars, line units, and line amounts. End-users then manually replicate these GE entries onto their respective excel files for operational reporting purposes. The excel files contain all the purchasing transactions generated by respective departments. The annual volume of expenditure reflects the level of contributions by end-user departments, in their endeavor to support and deliver academic programs of the university in an academic year.

To extract a pivot table or summarized report from these excel datasets is not possible. The only summarized reporting that can be generated is a one-liner of total expenditure for each department per academic year. For effective and swift decision-making, decision-makers and managers prefer high-level summarized information at some logical reporting levels than looking at detailed reports or one-liner reports. An extra reporting attribute, sufficient to enable drill-down reporting is needed for the current GE datasets.

The overall objective of the project is to develop a predictive text classification model, to analyse an expenditure text and assign appropriate labels from the two allowable class codes. Specifically, the project designs a structured GE dataset, to enable visibility on GE streams for reporting, accounting, and budgeting purposes. A new column is inserted as a reporting attribute beside each line item. Project GEML took these basic steps to achieve its objective:

- Step 1. Identify GE dataset and retrieve raw data from MCS department
- Step 2. Clean the dataset and merge into a single dataset
- Step 3. Manually label a portion of dataset
- Step 4. Use machine learning text classifier to train and test the model
- Step 5. Implement text classification on unlabelled dataset and assign appropriate labels

The actual implementation process is executed through the CRISP-DM cycle methodology. The project enables the Client fulfil some of its business objectives through summarised reporting by expenditure categories to realise: better evaluation and visibility on past spending; ability to provide accurate and timely reporting to the stakeholders; ability to make informed decisions on managing expenditure; accountability on acquittals and reporting; analysis on actual spending versus budget amounts.

2. Literature Review

Trivedi et al. (2015) presented their findings on an empirical study carried out on text classification algorithms by comparing three models Decision tree, Naïve Bayes and SVM. They discussed the results obtained from performing text classification on a clinical patient dataset. Machine learning was performed through Wekadata mining tool. Text classification was aimed at predicting whether the patient was tested positive/negative with diabetes mellitus disease based on the criteria set by World Health Organization. From the measures of Accuracy and F1 scores obtained, the authors recommended SVM as the best classifier model to solve text classification problems.

Sharka (2019) implemented text classification methods using Python programming language and its in-built libraries to classify free text fields into labelled categories. To build a learning machine system, the author uses a 67% of the original dataset to train the model, and 33% of the original dataset to test the model. The split ratio of 2/3 training and 1/3 testing is a widely recommended ratio in Machine learning space. The author provides a sample of python coding scripts to effect text classification in Python programming environment as an alternate back-end approach. Figure1 shows a workflow for building a standard text classification system with supervised learning (classification) models. The diagram illustrates the relationship between different aspects of text classification - training, testing, prediction, and evaluation (Sharka, 2019).

Russle and Norvig (2010) discussed the concepts of machine learning about learning from examples. An agent is learning if it improves its performance on future tasks after making observations about the world. In supervised learning, the agent observes some examples of input–output pairs and learns a function that maps from input to output. Any component of an agent can be improved by learning from past historical data because the more prior knowledge an agent has, the better the probability of an improved prediction outcome.

Figure 1: Text classification blue print

Riakert and Klein (2021) carried out text classification using Naïve Bayes and SVM text classifier model on a small dataset, as a baseline study to understand online media. They recommended text-based factors be incorporated into text classification modelling to improve predictions. Factors like n-gram, uni-gram and bi-gram are core functionalities that adds extra meanings apart from pure keywords lookups. N-gram is words or words sequences. For example: 1-gram (uni-gram) for single words, 2-gram (bi-gram) for two words combination, 3-gram for 3-word combination and so on. The findings reveal that: SVM classifier model performs better than Naïve Bayes; Bi-grams increased the accuracy in most experiments than uni-gram.

Zainal et al. (2015) used classification and clustering algorithms to classify spam messages from SMS (short message service) using two data mining software tools –Rapid Miner and Weka. From the simulations, both tools gave similar results confirming that classifier models are efficient algorithms to solve SMS spam classification and clustering problems. The SMS text messages utilises combination of keywords, semantics and linguistics. The authors demonstrated the use of data mining tools with reliable features to implement text classification and clustering.

Kulkarni and Shivananda (2019) described the process of exploring and processing of text data. The real-word dataset is usually unstructured and messy, and their paper discussed certain techniques to apply pre-processing to clean and prepare the dataset for modelling. Some of the common techniques applied on an unprocessed text are methods such as

conversions to lower/upper cases; removal of punctuations; removal of stop words; spelling corrections; and word tokenization.

Real-world data is often incomplete, inconsistent, and filled with a lot of noise and is likely to contain many errors impacting prediction outcomes. Pre-processing is a vital step in preparing text data for machine learning. Igual and Segui (2017) discussed tool boxes for data scientists and explained some of the specific toolkits and methods applied in machine learning:

SCIKIT-Learn in Python is a machine learning library built from NumPy, SciPy, and Matplotlib. Scikit-learn offers simple and efficient tools for common tasks in data analysis such as classification, regression, clustering, dimensionality reduction, model selection, and pre-processing.

Machine Learning is part of Artificial Intelligence (AI) that involves using programs that automatically adjust their performance in accordance with their exposure to information in data.

Confusion matrix is a table that measures modelling predictions. Although accuracy is the most normal metric for evaluating classifiers, there are cases when the business value of correctly predicting elements from one class is different from the value for the prediction of elements of another class. In those cases, accuracy is not a good performance metric and more detailed analysis is needed. The matrix considers the concepts of the classifier outcome and the actual ground truth or gold standard. In a binary problem, there are four possible cases:

- a) True Positive (TP): When the classifier predicts a sample as positive and it really is positive.
- b) False Positive (FP): When the classifier predicts a sample as positive but in fact it is negative. This is also known as a false alarm.
- c) True Negative (TN): When the classifier predicts a sample as negative and it really is negative.
- d) False Negative (FN): When the classifier predicts a sample as negative but in fact it is positive.

Table 1: Construction of a confusion matrix

		Actual (Gold Standard)	
		Positive	Negative
Prediction	Positive	TP	FP
	Negative	FN	FN

Confusion matrix is constructed using the four factors as in Table 1. The prediction outcomes are populated onto the matrix and performance of text classification is measured. Some common measurements are calculated using these formulas:

Accuracy = $\frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$. Accuracy is a fraction of correct predictions.

Sensitivity = $\frac{TP}{TP + FN}$. Sensitivity is a proportion of actual positives that are correctly identified as positives.

F1 score = $\frac{2TP}{2TP + FP + FN}$. F1 score is an averaged and balanced measure of accuracy.

3. Methodology

Project GEML followed the best practice Data Mining methodology known as CRISP-DM (Cross Industry Standard Process for Data Mining) through several phases as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: CRISP-DM methodology

3.1. Business Understanding

The Client is PNG University of Technology, a premier technological learning institution in PNG. Its core business operation is functionally segregated into two distinct groups, the academic departments and the non-academic departments. The disbursement of the annual operational funds for each department is managed through a GE process. GE requests are transacted on a monthly basis and/or ad-hoc basis throughout the course of an academic year. The two major types of expenditure items requested through GE are generally categorised as: Goods (tangible items) such as consumables, tools and equipment,

materials and supplies, and unplanned critical items; Services (non-tangible items) such as maintenance services on assets, consultation, training, admin and staff support, student support, and unplanned events.

The Client requires a model to classify existing GE datasets according to appropriate categories to enable a lower drill-down reporting of annual expenditure. Table 2 and Figure 3 show high-level summary on GE data for 2019 and 2020 for MCS department. The department expended K10,000 more in 2019 for the same number of line items. A further breakdown of the annual spending to analyse the variation is not possible.

Table 2: GE summary by year

GE-year	GE-lines	GE-amount (K)
2019	41	48,357
2020	41	37,610
Total	82	85,967

Figure 3: GE summary by year

Project GEML implemented text classification to enable another lower reporting level as in Table 3 and Figure 4. The graphs show a drilled down reporting by category levels for MCS in 2019 and 2020. The 82 lines on the GE dataset were manually labelled to illustrate the enhanced reporting structure. Figure 4 clearly shows the visibility of the breakdown to aid quick analysis.

Table 3: Enhanced summary table by category

GE-year	GE-category	GE-lines	GE-amount (K)
2019	Goods	24	31,182
	Services	17	17,175
2020	Goods	25	20,400
	Services	16	17,210
Total		82	85,967

Figure 4: Enhanced summary graph by category

3.2. Data understanding

MCS department uses an Excel file as data repository for all its GE transactions done annually each academic year. The excel table file is a replica of the manual GE form. The three attributes (dept, vendor, date) are header-fields meaning their entries are recorded once while the other three attributes (line No, particulars, amount) are detail-fields meaning they have distinct values for each line item. All the attributes do allow certain restrictions on them to control the type of entries they are expected to hold, while Particulars is a free text field.

Table 4 outlines the details of the enhanced GE-master table definition, showing its attribute names and the attribute definitions. GE-master table is an electronic replica of the physical GE form. The attribute GE-category is a new attribute that is inserted onto the excel table as a reporting attribute. It holds only two values of either a '1' for Goods or a '2' for Services.

Table 4: GE-master table

Attribute	Description of the attribute
GE-dept	Name of the department
GE-vendor	Supplier of goods & services
GE-date	Date of transaction
GE-lineNo	Line number
GE-particulars	Details of the expenditure line item
GE-category	Code that represents expenditure category of the line item. '1' - means Goods '2' - means Services
GE-amount	Requested amount for the line item

Table 5: Sample of GE dataset

Line No	Particulars	GE-amount (K)
1	Being for the Server maintenance	4,500
2	Network cables for the lab use	1,500
3	Carton of H2O/Trutru wara/Pure water	250
4	Trasportatin – Madang Trip – MCS Students	900

Table 5 is a sample of the raw expenditure line items from the 2019 GE dataset.

3.3. Data preparation

Project GEML was implemented with the use of necessary technical toolkits required for machine learning and data analytics:

- Python development environment: provided the coding environment to manipulate coding scripts
- Sci-Kit Learn: is a pre-coded machine learning library used to train and test the models
- Microsoft Excel: serves as the data source for the GE dataset in CSV format.

GE dataset contained 82 rows of raw data, got split into two separate datasets for training and testing. Training dataset consisted of 60-line items which are 70% of the original dataset, and testing dataset consists of 22-line items which are 30% of the original dataset. The new attribute GE-category was inserted next to Particulars to identify the type of expenditure item. Pre-processing technique was applied on the dataset as part of data preparation (Sarka, 2019).

Table 6: After pre-processing

Line No	Particulars	GE-amount (K)
1	Server, maintenance	4,500
2	Network Cables for the Lab Use	1,500
3	Water	250
4	Trasportation Madang Trip MCS Students	900

Table 6 shows a sample of the enhanced GE table, as a result of applying pre-processing on the raw sample in Table 5:

- 1) Conversion to upper cases on line 2 =>“NETWORK CABLES FOR THE LAB USE”
- 2) Removal of punctuations on line 4 =>“Trasportation Madang Trip MCS Students”

- 3) Removal of stop words on line 1 =>“Server maintenance”
- 4) Spelling corrections on line 4 =>“Transportation Madang Trip MCS Students”
- 5) Linguistic & semantics on line 3 => “H20, wara, water” are recognised as “Water”
- 6) Word tokenization after removal of stop words on line 1 => “Server”, “maintenance”

3.4. Modelling

Project GEML provided a cleansed GE dataset in CSV format as the input. The output is a revised GE dataset with a new reporting attribute. The two machine learning algorithms applied in text classification are SVM and Naïve Bayes. Figure 5 shows the overview of the modelling process.

Figure 5: Modelling process overview

Figure 6: An extended process of ‘text classification’

Nature of this prediction is binary classification (bi-nominal) as the expected outcome is either “1” (Goods) or “2” (Services). Figure 6 shows the detailed mechanics inside a typical text classification black box. The model used 70% of the input dataset and learned from past data. The learning was given extra meaning from effective use of analytical methods like n-gram, keywords, semantics and linguistics. The model used 1-gram in this setting. The other 30% of the dataset was used to test and evaluate the performance of the model. The Accuracy and F1 scores generated by the model provided the mechanism to evaluate its performance (Riakert and Klein, 2021).

4. Model evaluation

The TRUE classes of the dataset were labelled according to human judgment and therefore considered as the ground truth or gold standard in this project. The original labelled dataset was partitioned into a 70/30 ratio to train and test the model respectively. The training dataset trained the model, while the testing dataset tested and evaluated the text classifier against the gold standard to measure its performance (Igual and Segui, 2017).

Our aim was to build a text classifier to predict that an expenditure item was related to Goods (true cases), and so we expected the model to classify items related to Goods correctly. If the model failed to correctly predict items related to Goods, then the model incorrectly classified items as Services (false cases). Similarly, if we flipped our target and expected the model to predict items related to Services (true cases) correctly, incorrect predictions would be labelled as Goods (false cases). A new set of 100 randomly selected records from GE-dataset were fed into the model for text classification. Outputs from the modelling were measured using the confusion matrix, and the results were as follows:

Table 7: Confusion matrix from Naïve Bayes model

		Actual	
		Goods (true)	Services (false)
Predicted	Goods (true)	11 (TP)	04 (FP)
	Services (false)	05 (FN)	80 (TN)

Table 8: Confusion matrix table from SVM model

		Actual	
		Goods (true)	Services (false)
Predicted	Goods (true)	20 (TP)	05 (FP)
	Services (false)	04 (FN)	71 (TN)

Table 9: Performance comparison table

Model	Correctly classified	Incorrectly classified	Total samples	Accuracy %	F1 score %
Naïve Bayes	87	13	100	87	65
SVM	91	09	100	91	81

Table 7 and Table 8 show the confusion matrix for SVM and Naïve Bayes classifiers respectively. Table 9 shows the performance matrix of the two classifiers. F1 score is usually the preferred measure to evaluate model performances. The tables indicated that there were both correctly and incorrectly predicted outcomes. Accuracy measures both cases as correctly predicted but it is not really true so F1 score somewhat provides an

unbiased measure. SVM has again proven to be the best classifier with an F1 score of 81% than Naïve Bayes scoring 65%. Similar modelling approach was performed and discussed by Igoal and Segui (2017).

Accuracy = $(TP + TN) / (TP + TN + FP + FN)$. Accuracy is the fraction of the correct predictions.

F1 Score = $2TP / (2TP + FP + FN)$ - A balanced and un-biased measure of accuracy.

The final product of project GEML was a revised GE dataset with an extra GE-category attribute with two allowable values. Table 10 is a sample of the revised GE dataset showing GE-category and the corresponding reporting values.

Table 10: Sample of the output dataset

Line No	Particulars	GE-category	GE-amount (K)
1	Being for the Server maintenance	1-Services	4,500
2	Network cables for the lab use	2-Goods	1,500
3	Overhead projectors for lecture rooms	2-Goods	2,200
4	Trasportatin–Madang Trip–MCS Students	1-Services	900

4.1. Deployment

The roll-out of project GEML will begin at the MCS department and extend to other participating departments at PNGUoT. The feedbacks from these initial rollouts will provide baseline to leverage extensive improvements in order to deliver improved machine learning solutions.

The best performing SVM text classifier is expected to correctly classify about 80% of the cases, while the 20% incorrectly classified lines will be manually evaluated and labelled. If each department generate around 40 GE lines annually on average, the total volume of lines to be classified through Machine learning is estimated to be 800 GE lines from the 20 different functional departments of PNGUoT. Applying text classification on 800 lines of annual GE datasets for the Client, will result in about 600 (80%) lines being correctly labelled while the 200 (20%) incorrectly labelled lines will require human evaluation and labelling.

5. Conclusion

Project GEML’s objective was to develop a reliable predictive labelling model to assign expenditure items into two categories, based on free text descriptions. By applying pre-

processing, filtering, and analysing GE's Particulars free text data, the Project demonstrated that such a classification model in Machine learning is achievable. Using this project as the baseline study, there are opportunities in the near future to enhance text classification modelling in similar machine learning and/or data mining projects.

One possible area would be to develop another lower level of summarised reporting on the GE dataset. The two reporting categories developed by GEML forms the 2nd reporting level but it can be further drilled-down to a 3rd reporting level. As such enables an orderly and structured summary reporting break-up from level-1 (by year), down to level-2 (by year by category), and finally to level-3 (by year by category by sub-category). Sub-categories would identify reporting items such as:

- Staff, support, Admin support, Asset maintenance within the Services category.
- Office consumables, Furniture, Equipment within the Goods category.

Another area of future work would be to investigate other data sources at PNGUoT that requires data cleansing and apply machine learning to clean and restructure existing data and datasets. A good example is the Maintenance and Inventory database system operated and managed by the Grounds & Estate department.

References

Igual, L. and Segui, S., 2017, *Introduction to Data Science: A Python Approach to Concepts, Techniques and Applications*, Springer.

Kulkarni, A. and Shivananda, A., 2019, *Natural Language Processing Recipes. Unlocking Text Data with Machine Learning and Deep Learning using Python*, Springer.

Riakert, M. and Klein, A., 2021, *Simple Baseline Machine Learning Text Classifiers for Small Datasets*, SN Computer Science, Springer.

Russle, S. and Norvig, P., 2010, *Artificial Intelligence. A modern approach*, Third Edition, Pearson Education.

Sarka, D., 2019, *Text Analytics with Python. A Practitioner's Guide to Natural Language Processing*, Second Edition, Springer.

Trivedi, M. Soni, N. Sharma, S. and Nair, S., 2015, Comparison of Text Classification Algorithms. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology*, 4, 334-336.

Zainal, K., Sulaiman, N.F. and Zali, M.F., 2015, An Analysis of Various Algorithms for Text Spam Classification and Clustering Using Rapid Miner and Weka. *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security*, 13, 66-74.